

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13902214>

IMPORTANCE OF FAIRY TALES IN TEACHING SECOND LANGUAGE

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Abstract: Fairy tales might be considered one of the possible supplementary teaching materials for English language learners. They may contribute to the enrichment of a young reader’s knowledge in a number of ways. Children’s fairy tales teach moral and standards of language existence. In addition to that, tales are a particular type of text which can be adapted to suit the child’s age. They are also a great source of vocabulary, grammar structures and help to develop all for skills.

Fairy tales are very important for children in learning their mother tongue, and they are important in learning any foreign language as well. That is why it is good to start using fairy tales in teaching English as soon as possible. Primary school children enjoy listening to fairy tales over and over again. This frequent repetition allows certain language items to be acquired while others are being overtly reinforced. Many fairy tales contain natural repetition of key vocabulary and structures. This helps children to remember every detail, so they can gradually learn to anticipate what is about to happen next in the fairy tales. Repetition also encourages participation in the narrative”.

According to Ellis & Brewster, 2002, p 103-107. Fairy tales are very motivating, challenging and great fun for children. They can help develop positive attitudes towards the foreign language, culture and language learning. Using fairy tales allows the teacher to introduce or revise new vocabulary and sentence structures by exposing the children to language in varied, memorable and familiar contexts, which will enrich their thinking and gradually enter their own speech. Listening to fairy tales helps children become aware of the rhythm, intonation and pronunciation of language. Fairy tales also provide opportunities for developing continuity in children’s learning. They can link English with other subject areas across the curriculum.

When children listen to fairy tales in class they share social experience, it provokes a shared response of laughter, sadness, excitement and anticipation which is not only enjoyable but can help to build up the child’s confidence and encourage social and emotional development. “Fairy tales are a useful tool in linking fantasy and the

imagination with the child's real world. They provide a way of enabling children to make sense of their everyday life and forge links between home and school".

Children exercise their imagination through fairy tales. They "can become personally involved in a fairy tales as they identify with the characters and try to interpret the narrative and illustrations. This imaginative experience helps" students develop their own creative potential.

Fairy tales also "develop the different types of 'intelligences' that contribute to language learning, including emotional intelligence". Fairy tales "develop children's learning strategies such as listening for general meaning, predicting, guessing meaning and hypothesizing". Fairy tales can develop all children's skills.

Tales address universal themes which go beyond the useful level of basic dialogues and daily activities. "They allow children to play with ideas and feelings and to think about issues which are important and relevant to them". They also provide "ideal opportunities for presenting cultural information and encouraging cross-cultural comparison".

For teachers Fairy tales allow "to use an acquisition-based methodology by providing optimal input". It is great to use real fairy tales books because they "add variety and provide a springboard for creating complete units of work that constitute mini-syllabuses and involve pupils personally, creatively actively in an all-round whole curriculum approach. They thereby provide a novel alternative to the coursebook".

Fairy tales are largely based on words. They give meaning to words. "Learning English through Fairy tales can lay the foundations for secondary school in terms of learning basic language functions and structures, vocabulary and language learning skills". (Phillips, S. 2013) It is obvious that we should choose different types of Fairy tales and different topics for primary school students. Also the sources of Fairy tales are different. Students are able to create their own Fairy tales if they have the right input.

The use of a fairy tale as a pedagogical instrument is linked especially to the development of children's literature in the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries, which itself changes in concepts of childhood and children. Fairy tales were soon enlisted in the services of teaching children. For example Jeanne-Marie Leprince de Beaumont, who worked as a governess in England, published a series of pedagogical works targeting specific ages and social classes, such as *Le magasin de enfants* and *Le magasin des adolescents*, which included several fairy tales in order to teach children social values and virtues. Also, in the nineteenth-century in Germany, Jacob and Wilhelm Grimm conceived their *Children's and Household Tales*, as a tool of national pedagogy. The Grimms viewed their collection of fairy tales as a part of a project to reaffirm the cultural identity of the German folk. They meant that their collection of

fairy tales were not only teaching useful social, moral and religious lessons for children, but also they intended to educate the German people about German character and culture (Haase, 2008; Davidson & Chaudhri, 2003, p 25-45).

Reasons for using fairy tales

Children enjoy listening to tales in their mother tongue. Storytelling is an ideal introduction to foreign languages as they provide a familiar context for the child. Children start enjoying literature from an early age by the teacher's use of extensive reading of fairy tales. They develop their literary competence – a combination of linguistic, socio-cultural, historical and semiotic awareness. Literature, in general, allows pupils to understand and appreciate cultures and ideologies different from their own. Consequently, children learn to respect other cultures and to be involved in them. In addition to this, storytelling provides contexts for talking, listening, reading, writing and other activities such as dance and drama.

According to several critics there are a number of reasons why teachers use children's fairy tales:

- Fairy tales are motivating and fun creating a desire to communicate. They develop positive attitudes and help children to keep on learning. Positive affective factors facilitate acquiring a second language. Children will learn better if they have a positive attitude towards what they are doing.

- Fairy tales exercise the imagination. Children imagine sceneries, characters and soon about a story. For example, if they become personally involved in a story they can identify with some characters.

- Fairy tales provide a rich resource for education about human societies, offering insights into life in many different communities and into complex cultures.

- Fairy tales are a useful tool in linking fantasy and imagination with the child's real world. So children can make sense of their everyday life. Fairy tales help children to understand the world and to share it with others. "Nine to twelve -year-olds are developing their ability to appreciate other viewpoints. At this age fairy tales about family and friends should not only reassure children about themselves but also provide them with new insights into how other families and children cope with various situations. Children at this age enjoy fairy tales that extend their experiences. On the other hand, there is a need to make language learning easier for young children by relating it to their experience in everyday life.

- Literature has a social and emotional value, which is a vital part of its role in the development of children's language learning skills and literacy. Listening to fairy tales in class is a shared social experience. Storytelling provokes a response of laughter, sadness, excitement and anticipation, which can encourage the child's social and emotional development. In addition, there is always a sort of interaction between the

reader and his listeners so s/he can ask for the listeners' collaboration to say what happens next, for instance. Listening to fairy tales is a natural way of acquiring language. The child learns to deduce what happens next, to deduce the meaning of words from the context or visual aids. This helps to build their confidence. Moreover, children need to develop a series of characteristics to enable them to fit into the society they live in, to become aware of themselves in relation to others, to share and cooperate. They can achieve this by listening to fairy tales. For instance, children learn about other experiences and they can compare those experiences with theirs.

– Children enjoy listening to fairy tales over and over again. This allows certain language items to be acquired while others are being overtly reinforced. Little by little they make sense out of the listening. In addition, repetition also encourages participation in the narrative, thereby providing a type of pattern practice in a meaningful context.

– Telling fairy tales is an example of input – input of language through listening and reading – for the child to activate and develop his own learning mechanisms. Moreover, the process of making input comprehensible is an active constructive process. An important condition for language acquisition to occur is that the student understands input language that contains a structure 'a bit beyond' his/her current level of competence. So they can understand most of it but still be challenged to make progress (Brown 1987: 188). Neither should the input be so easy as to make the learner become bored because there is nothing new for him/her. Fairy tales introduce some new vocabulary and sentence structures. In general terms, children acquire first the general semantic characteristics of words (Galeote 2002: 167). Their meanings are contextualized and can be inferred from the pictures or teacher's gestures. Moreover, the teacher usually reads slowly and gives them time to think about the meaning and look at the pictures. Many traditional fairy tales are bound with powerfully repeated phrases such as Goldilocks – Who's been sitting on my chair? And who's broken it? Added baby bear... Who's been sleeping in my bed? Baby bear adds: and who's still sleeping there now? These examples can be used as an almost subliminal grammar input.

Moreover, the use of these fairy tales, for example, which usually contains a lot of direct speech, helps the learner develop a sense of how intonation is used to express attitudes and feelings.

– fairy tales can be used to reinforce conceptual development in children (colour, shape, time, size etc.).

– fairy tales are a way of getting children to learn for themselves. That is the case with the following:

Reinforcing thinking strategies (comparing, classifying, predicting, planning etc.)

Developing strategies for learning English (guessing the meaning of new words, training the memory etc.)

Developing study skills (understanding and interpreting charts and graphs, organizing work and so on.).

– Using tales is a powerful way of helping pupils to learn in all areas of the curriculum. According to Howe and Johnson (1992: 5), the reason is that narrative is a universal way of organising events and ideas. Fairy tales can be chosen to consolidate learning in school subjects across the curriculum, which is appropriate to the pupil's cognitive level.